

Lagrangian Extremization from Special Relativity? Part II

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In Part I, we focused on the special relativistic Lorentz invariants $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$) and $(E-V)^2 = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$). We argued that these together with the variable switching forms (familiar in thermodynamics e.g. $E(S,V)$ but $F=E-TS \rightarrow F(T,V)$) i.e. $E = -L_1(v) + pv$ and $(E-V) = -L_1(v) + pv$ lead to $p = \partial L / \partial v$ (partial). From this, one may show using the variable switching forms that an equation of motion follows from the extremization of L .

Here we focus instead on the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ (for a free particle) which we write as: $L_1(v)t = t(-E + pv)$ and $L_1(v)t = t(-(E-V) + pv)$ for a particle with a potential. We show again that $\partial L / \partial v = p$ from which the extremization of $L = L_1 - V$ follows. Interestingly, this same Lorentz invariant with another partial derivative linked to p , namely Action $= Lt = -Et + px \rightarrow dAction/dx = p$. In this case, the independent variables differ.

Forming an eigenvalue equation: $-i\partial/dx \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ leads to quantum mechanics. This time, in the case of a potential one cannot simply use $E \rightarrow E-V(x)$ as many $\exp(ipx)$ s are stirred up to create the distribution $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. If one, however, uses $-i\partial/dx$ as a momentum operator (which follows from $-i\partial/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$) and applies this to the Lorentz operator: $(E-V)(E-V) = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$) then one obtains the Klein-Gordon equation $(\partial^2/\partial t^2 - \partial^2/\partial x^2 - V) W = -d^2W/dx^2 + m^2 W$. Thus a quadratic form holds with $E-V$, but the linear form $-Et + px$ only holds for a single p in the quantum (but not the classical) case.

Lagrangian

In classical physics, a Lagrangian is usually written as kinetic energy - $V(x)$ (potential energy) and is varied together with constraints. L is a function of x, v, t . If t is not present, then extremization leads to:

$$d/dt \partial L / \partial v - \partial L / \partial x = 0 \quad ((1))$$

It seems, however, that in classical physics a variation of $L(x, v, t)$ is taken as a starting point and associated with the idea of considering all possible paths from a start to an end point, and then choosing a stationary one. The justification seems to be that this yields Newton's second law, which in turn is experimentally verifiable.

Here we argue (as in Part I) that the extremization of the Lagrangian follows from special relativity.

We note in particular that the Lagrangian depends on $v = dx/dt$ i.e. there is a deterministic relationship between x and t in this view.

Lagrangian Extremization from the Lorentz Invariant $-Et+px$

In Part I, we considered the Lorentz invariants $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ and $(E-V)(E+V) = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ and showed that in both cases: $dL/dv = p$ where $E = -L_1(v) + pv$ or $(E-V) = -L_1(v) + pv$. From this, we demonstrated that the extremum of L led to an equation of motion.

Here we consider instead the Lorentz invariant:

$$\text{Action (free particle)} = L_1 t = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

If one divides by t , then $v=x/t$. This procedure emphasizes the dependence of x on t and so is classical in nature. (In classical mechanics, the goal is to find $x(t)$.) Thus:

$$L_1(v) t = -E + pv \quad ((3)) \quad \rightarrow \quad dL_1/dv = p \quad ((4))$$

((4)) utilizes the derivative of L_1 and p is a constant. Thus: $d/dt (dL_1/dv) = 0$. This, however, is of the form of variational principle i.e.

$$d/dt (dL_1/dv) \rightarrow dL_1/dv \delta x/dt \quad ((5))$$

An integration by parts leads to $-\frac{d}{dt} (dL_1/dv) \delta x$.

Thus one varies the path i.e. δx . One may note that variation of the path follows from the fact that $dp/dt = 0$ because p is a constant i.e. a conserved quantity. The fact that p may be written in terms of dL_1/dv sets the stage for the variational principle because v contains d/dt i.e. $v=dx/dt$.

Thus the key idea is that $p = dL_1/dv$ which follows directly from the Lorentz invariant ((2)) i.e. special relativity.

In the case of a potential $V(x)$ ((2)) becomes:

$$L_1(v)t = -(E-V)t + px \quad ((6)) \quad \text{This leads to: } dL_1/dv = dV/dx + p \text{ for } V(x) \text{ or:}$$

$$dL/dv = p \text{ where } L = L_1 - V(x) \quad ((7))$$

Once again, there exists the Lagrangian relationship with p . From Newton's second law $dp/dt = -dV/dx$ there is extremization of the Lagrangian because $d/dt (dL/dv)$ is part of an extremization term if one uses integration by parts. Thus dp/dt is a fundamental form from Newtonian mechanics which applies both in the case of $V(x)$ and without, but $p=dL/dv$ from special relativity ensures $d/dt (dL/dv)$ is of the form of an extremization with δx , the path, being varied.

Quantum Mechanics

It is interesting to note that not only does $-Et+px = \text{Action}$ yield the extremization procedure of the Lagrangian, but it also results in quantum mechanics. One may see both Lagrangian theory

and quantum mechanics appear from the same Lorentz invariant. A key difference in quantum mechanics is that one ignores the relationship $v=dx/dt$ i.e. one does not divide the action by t and use $v=x/t$. Rather x and t are kept independent. Then:

$$dAction/dx \text{ partial} = p \quad ((8))$$

Once again, there exists a partial derivative of a function which equals momentum, but the derivative is now different. d/dx partial instead of d/dv partial applies and the independent variables are x,t instead of x,v . Thus classical physics focuses on $x(t)$ and v , while quantum mechanics, on fluctuations with x,t independent. On average, however, $v=x/t = \text{constant}$.

One may proceed to form an eigenvalue equation:

$$-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((9a)) \quad \text{Similarly} \quad id/dt \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(iEt) \quad ((9b))$$

In this case, no extremization has been used. One may note that a constant p is now associated with a range of x i.e. a wavelength (\hbar/p) and not a point x . This leads to a radical change from classical mechanics. If p has an x range, one cannot have $p(x)$ because each changing p has its own range. (It might, however, be possible to have some kind of average link with $p(x)$.) If one takes ((9a)) seriously, then it seems one must form a p average:

$$P \text{ average} = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ p a(p) \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \} = -id \ln W/dx$$

$$\text{where } W = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad \text{and } a(p) \text{ are weights} \quad ((10))$$

In the quantum case: $Action(p) = -Et + px$, E,p constant only applies to a constant p , not $p(x)$ as it does classically. How does one then determine $a(p)$? If one notes that $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant then:

$$M_0 t_0 = -Et + px \quad ((11)), \text{ but } t_0 \text{ is arbitrary.}$$

There is, however, another Lorentz invariant which does not have arbitrariness, namely:

$$M_0 m_0 = -EE + pp \quad (c=1) \quad ((12))$$

If $-id/dx$ is the p operator, then $pp = -d/dx d/dx$ and ((12)) yields the Klein-Gordon equation:

$$-d/dt dW(x,t)/dt = m_0 m_0 W(x,t) - d/dx d/dx W(x,t) \quad ((13))$$

In the nonrelativistic limit, this yields the Schrodinger equation.

Quantum mechanical results may be obtained without using extremization. There is however, an extremization principle buried in the above approach (2) because one moves from the operator $-id/dx$ which is linked with the first Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ to $-d/dx d/dx$ which is found in the second Lorentz invariant ((12)).

In terms of extremization this may be written as:

$$dW/dx \rightarrow \text{extremize} \rightarrow -d/dx dW/dx \quad ((14))$$

$$\text{And: } dW/dx \rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} \ln(WW) \rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} \ln(WW) \quad ((15))$$

((15)) is called Fisher's information in statistics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Lorentz invariant Action = $L t = -Et + px$ may be used to obtain the extremization of a Lagrangian as well as quantum mechanics. In the Lagrangian case, for a free particle one associates x and t i.e. $x(t)$ which is classical. Then $L_1(v) = -E + pv$ for a free particle and $dL_1/dv = p$. Using $dp/dt = 0$ yields $d/dt dL_1/dv = 0$ which is part of an extremization scheme i.e. $dL/dv \partial \Delta v = -d/dt dL_1/dv \partial \Delta x$.

In the case of a potential: $L_1(v) = -(E-V) + pv$ and $dL/dv = p$ where $L = L_1 - V$. Using $dp/dt = -dV/dx$ again leads to an extremization scheme.

It is interesting to note that the same Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ which is associated with Lagrangian extremization, also yields quantum mechanics. Again a partial derivative is linked to p , but in this case x and t are independent, breaking the classical $x(t)$ view. $dAction/dx = p$ for a free particle.

If one creates an eigenfunction equation $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$, then a constant p is associated with repeated x ranges i.e. wavelength (\hbar/p) Thus p is not associated with a point any longer, although on average $x = vt$, $v = \text{constant}$. As a result, there is no point writing $-(E-V)t + p(x)x$ because x does not change at a point due to the wavelength.

One approach is to create an average of $\exp(ipx)$ s i.e. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$. One may then use a second Lorentz invariant $\text{momo} = -(E-V)(E-V) + pp$ with $E = id/dt$ and $p = -id/dx$. This leads to a second order differential equation i.e. the Klein-Gordon equation which yields the Schrodinger equation in the nonrelativistic limit. No extremization has been used, Implicitly, however, there is a variational procedure because one goes from $-id/dx$ introduced in $-Et + px$ to $-d/dx d/dx$ in $(E-V)(E-V) = pp + \text{momo}$. In terms of extremization, this may be written as: $dW/dx \rightarrow \text{extremize} \rightarrow d/dx dW/dx$ where dW/dx is proportional to Fisher's information in statistics.

References

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